

DETERMINANTS OF LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG ABOUT TO RETIRE CIVIL SERVANTS IN LAGOS STATE

Olori Alao Olusola Adedoyin
Department Of Business Administration
University Of Lagos, Nigeria.

Ishola, Ajibola Abdulrahamon
Department of Psychology,
University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

Kenku, Akeem, A. Ph.D
Department of Psychology,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Nasarawa State University, Keffi. Nigeria

and

Aroyewun, Temitope Folashade
Department of Psychology,
University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Pre-retirement life satisfaction is a key issue to human resource management as it affects overall wellbeing in the public service. Career transition, job satisfaction and pre-retirement satisfaction relationships have not been explored in extant literatures. This study examined the determinants of life satisfaction among civil servants nearing retirement in Lagos State. Four hundred and Eight-eight (488) employees-close-to-retirement were selected from target ministries, and were sampled through a multi-stage sampling procedure. A self-report questionnaire was used to collect the data which was analysed using descriptive statistics and PPMC correlation analysis. Job satisfaction, Career transition readiness, and Self-efficacy were positive correlates of life satisfaction. In addition, self-esteem and career support had inverse relationship with Life Satisfaction. It was concluded that employees with high self-confidence, transition ready and positive job satisfaction were more satisfied with life. These have implication retaining managerial talents, creating bridge work and career transition in the public service.

Keywords: Life satisfaction, Job Satisfaction, Career Transition Readiness, Self-Efficacy, Self-Esteem, Career Support, Lagos State Public Service.

INTRODUCTION

Pre-retirement life satisfaction is a key issue to human resource management as it affects overall wellbeing of public servants. Career transition, job satisfaction and pre-retirement satisfaction relationships have not been explored in extant literatures. However, life satisfaction among about to retire have been identified as a key issue in human resource management as it affects the psychological wellbeing of people at work. Satisfaction with life represents the cognitive process in which the current situation is appraised by contrasting it with an external basis of comparison according to Russell (1984). Scholars like Pivot and Diner (2008) viewed satisfaction with life as a core aspect of subjective wellbeing and a key measure of psychological health. Satisfaction with life seems to function as an intrapersonal strength that provides shield against the development of psychopathology in the face of increasing stressful life challenges (McKnight, Huebner, and Seldom, 2002). Likewise dimensions of career transition, that is, behavioural predispositions leading to engagement in proactive strategies toward retirement. These are psychological resources believed to improve organisational wellbeing during career transition.

Career transition dimensions are identified to be five. These include; readiness, efficacy, control, perceived social support, and decision independence. Career readiness, reflects how the individual perceives his or her readiness to make a career transition. Readiness is believed to be internal processes that energise and direct behaviour. Robinson (2010) has identified its crucial role in satisfaction with life for military men who recently changes their roles. The second factor, career confidence, assesses how much efficacy a person feels towards completing the tasks necessary to make a successful career transition. Perceived self-efficacy as "belief in one's capability to organise and execute the course of action required to produce given attainments". This plays a key role in career development, pursuits having implications for satisfaction with life among employees (Robertson, 2010). The third factor is the perception of control over the career transition experience. Central to the successful outcome of transition is the sense that one has control over this period of change and that one has the skills and knowledge required to handle the change associated with this (Robertson, 2010). The fourth factor is that of career social support. There is longstanding evidence to support the view that social processes play an important role in managing life transitions. "The adequacy and stability of social support as a determinant of objective and subjective wellbeing, of performance in major social roles, and of success in managing change in those roles. The fifth factor identified by Heppner, Malton, and Johnston,(1994) is that of decision independence, that is, whether the individual perceives the career transition decision as an independent or autonomous one, or a decision made in consideration of the needs of others.

The non-transition variables include the self-esteem. This is define has individuals perception of self-worth which implications for how much the values their achievement in life and present contribution in the organisation. Employees with high self-esteem are believed to have high satisfaction with life compared to others (Asuquo, 2007). To the knowledge of the researcher no studies have looked at these factors in the context of the Nigerian public service. Life satisfaction has received less attention among employees nearing retirement among employees in the public service compared to employees in the private sector such that job satisfaction is hampered and by extension, future life aspirations and satisfaction with life of about to retire employees are left to faith. Government at federal, state and local level have failed to provide the

safety net that will cater for ageing workforce as evident in the rates of protest and demonstrations over unpaid pensions. As such, there is stagnation, lack of candour and inconsistencies along the career path, self-esteem and self-efficacy, perhaps, making majority of them to experience poor condition of health, becoming unnecessarily aggressive and tendency of engaging in other form of anti-social vices.

The relationship between variables in the study was modelled after the Crisis theory which hinges on the notion life is about substituting one role for another (Friedman and Havighurst, 1954). The occupational role is regarded as the major source of cultural and personal validation and functions as the nexus around which all other roles rotate within an industrial society (Miller, 1965). This viewpoint, therefore, foresees that retirement from one role negatively affects self-identity, which in turn can disturb other roles as well. Successful adjustment is also predicated on the capability to substitute significant actions for the work role (Kosloski, Ginsburg, and Backman, 1984). The relevance of this theory in this study relates to the issue that an individual who is accustomed to normal work schedule as a way of life. Who are well adjusted to the change to come and are well prepared with adequate psychological and career resources will be happier in their life compared to those who entered into retirement without being prepared for it. Therefore, those retiree who are not prepared to quit active work life may experience some challenges in the absence of bridge work that can occupy his/her time, and hence develop some form of dissatisfaction after retirement.

On the contrary, Wang (2007) states that there is possibility that the effect of retirement on satisfaction with life is more heterogeneous. Amaike and Lai (2014) conducted a study to examine gender differentials in retirement antecedents and satisfaction with life of formal sector retirees in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study discovered that the retirement experiences of men and women were significantly related relatively because of massive informal supports women received as mentors and care givers. Similarly, they reported that women's involvement in social activities also afforded them the opportunity to access both material and non-material resources, which significantly improved their living conditions and satisfaction with life. Explicitly, they reported that retirement antecedents (such as level of income, social support etc.) are important predictors of satisfaction with life in retirement.

More painful, is the fact that in Nigeria, the prevailing corruption and mal-administration in the pension system has put fear in the mind of about to retire employees. In this sense, many employees prefer to hang on to their jobs and lie about their age because of the dread of life after retirement. Day in day out people constantly read and see thousands of retired Nigerian workers who are entitled to pension benefits, who have not received their gratuity several years after retirement. Those that are paid received meagre amount that could not take care of their daily expenses. It is against this backdrop that, the purpose of this study is to investigate psycho-social predictors of job and satisfaction with life among pre-retirement employees among civil servant in Lagos State, Nigeria. The significance of this study is further highlighted when one considers the substantial life that has been lost due to lack of consciousness and attention to employees' organizational career growth, and pre-retirement training thereby resulting into poor pre-retirement life and satisfaction with life among Nigerian retirees.

Method

Research Design

This study investigate the psycho-social determinants of satisfaction with life among about to retire civil servants in Lagos state. The study adopted cross-sectional survey research design with

the use of questionnaire to generate data and response from the research participants. The research was carried out in ministries and parastatals in Lagos State, which include ministries of Health, Education, Sports and Culture, Agriculture, Finance, Works and Housing and others.

Study Population

The population of the study includes all employees which are five years and below to their retirement in ministries and parastatals in Lagos State, Nigeria. The respondents were selected from employees who are about to retire from eight ministries which include ministries of Health, Education, Sports and Culture, Agriculture, Finance, Works and Housing and others.

Sample Size Estimation

Daniel and Terrel (2006) advanced the formula below for estimating sample size across multiple clusters;

$$n = \frac{Z^2 r^2}{d^2}$$

r= population of variability (variance) = (standard deviation) ² But r is always unknown and has to be estimated through: Pilot survey, similar studies and through the formula $V=R\sigma^2$. d= discrepancy i.e. the level of error to be tolerated between the true value and the estimated value.

Variance= Range where Range= Highest - Lowest. Thus the study sample size n = 548.85 approximate = 549

Participants and sampling

The total number of employees' close-to-retirement staff (Those given retirement notice) serve as the sample size in the distribution of the questionnaires. In line with Otokiti (2005), this study considers the best sample size is a complete census of the population and that all the elements of the population are expected to be included in the survey. This will make the sample statistics valid estimates of the population parameters.

Table 1 :(Sample Distribution, questionnaire retrieved and Analyse at a Glance)

S/N	Ministries	Population	% of the Total Population	Proportion in the sample overall sample size
1	Health	250	20	110
2	Education	450	36	198
3	Sports and Culture	200	16	88
4	Agriculture	150	12	66
5	Finance,	100	8	44
6	Works and Housing	100	8	44
	Total	1250	100	549

Source: Field Survey, (2016)

Instrumentation

The instrument asked questions the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants. These include: Age, sex, education qualification, year of experience, income, marital status and educational qualification. The items on the questionnaire were adapted from previous validated studies. Career transition was measured using career transitions inventory (CTI). The CTI originally had six constructs: (a) self-efficacy, (b) self-versus-relational focus, (c) motivation, (d) rational beliefs, (e) risk-taking, and (f) control. Reliability of the sub-dimensions ranged from .66 to .87 (median .69). The subscales of the CTI were positively correlated with the scales from the *My Vocational Situation* and the *Hope Scale* assessments (Heppner, Malton, and Johnston, 1994). Self-esteem was measured using self-esteem scale 10- item scale developed by Rosenberg's (1965). Sample items include; I feel that I am person of worth, comparable to others; I feel confident at any times. The scoring format was anchored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1= strongly agree to 5 = strongly disagree. The reliability of the scale as reported by the author is 0.82. Items 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 had to be reversed. Higher scores indicate a higher global self-esteem. Self-efficacy was measured using Judge et al., (1998) 8-item measure self-efficacy scale. The measure includes: I often feel that there is nothing that I cannot do very well. The scale was anchored on a 5-point scale Likert response format ranged from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The items within each scale were averaged to form a single score for generalized self-efficacy. Judge et al., (1998) reported 0.88 alpha as reliability for the scale. High scores on the scale represent increasing confidence and self-directed behaviour among the employees. Job Satisfaction was captured using items adapted from the short form 20-item Minnesota satisfaction scale developed by Weiss, Dawis, England and Lofquist (1967). The scale is made up of two dimensions; intrinsic or extrinsic satisfaction. Responses was scored on a Likert format ranged 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Reliability for the intrinsic scale was reported to be .86; .80 for the extrinsic subscale; .90 for the overall satisfaction scale.

Procedure

The researcher sought the necessary approval from the head of service through formal request. When the approval is granted, the researcher personally administer the questionnaires to the about to retire employees at their various offices. The researcher first obtained a verbal consent from the respondent after explaining to the respondents the nature of the research and that the study will be strictly for research purpose only. These steps were considered essential because of the seeming difficulties inherent in seeking cooperation assistance from workers.

Data Analysis

Data was analysis was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 17. Descriptive statistics (frequency, mean, and standard deviation) is used to offer a snapshot of the basic characteristics of the respondents' demographics. Thereafter, inferential statistics were conducted using correlation and regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Frequency count and percentage were used to analyze respondents' demographic information (age, gender, educational qualification, designation and length of service).

Table 2: Socio Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

	Category	Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	315	59.7
	Female	213	40.3
Age	Below 50 years	129	24.4
	50 – 55 years	198	37.5
	56 – 60 years	201	38.1
Religion	Christianity	327	61.9
	Islam	195	36.9
	Others	6	1.1
Marital Status	Single	44	8.3
	Married	448	84.8
	Divorced	15	2.8
	Widow(er)	21	4.0
Educational Qualification	O' Level	166	31.4
	OND/NCE	87	16.5
	HND	87	16.5
	B.Sc.	93	17.6
	M.Sc./MBA	47	8.9
	Post Graduate	18	3.4
	Professional Qualification	30	5.7

The Table 2 shows that a larger percentage of the respondent (59.7%) were male, a significant percentage of the respondents (38.1%) were between the age brackets of 56-60, a larger percentage of the respondent (61.9%) reported that they believed in Christianity, a larger percentage of the respondent (84.8%) reported that they were married, a significant percentage of the respondent (31.4%) reported that they have O'level as their educational qualification.

Table 3: Socio economic Characteristics of Respondents

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percent
Below 20 years	115	21.8
20-25 years	108	20.5
26 – 30 years	137	25.9
31 – 35 years	144	27.3
Above 35 years	21	4.0
Monthly Income		
N18,000 – N 50,000	195	36.9

N51,000 – N 100,000	210	39.8
N101,000 – N 150,000	39	7.4
N151, 000 – N 200,000	30	5.7
N201, 000 – N 300,000	33	6.3
N301, 000 – N 500,000	18	3.4
Social Economic Class		
Low-Low	68	12.9
Low-Middle	108	20.5
Low-High	36	6.8
Middle-Low	79	15.0
Middle-Middle	99	18.8
Middle-High	66	12.5
High-Low	27	5.1
High-Middle	30	5.7
High-High	15	2.8

The table shows that a significant percentage of the respondent (27.3%) reported that their year of experience is between 26-30 years, a significant percentage of the respondent (39.8%) reported that their monthly income is between N51, 000 – N 100,000; a significant percentage of the respondent (46.3%) reported that they belong to the middle social economic class.

Table 4: Perception of life satisfaction among respondents

	Very dissatis fying	Dissatisf ying	Rather dissatis fying	Rather satisfyin g	Satisfyin g	Very satisfyin g
Vocational situation	6(1.1)	2(.4)	6(1.1)	199(37.7)	183(34.7)	132(25.0)
Life as a whole	4(.8)	4(.8)		135(25.6)	271(51.3)	114(21.6)
Financial situation	36(6.8)	4(.8)	79(15.0)	198(37.5)	186(35.2)	25(4.7)
leisure situation	33(6.3)	5(.9)	48(9.1)	219(41.5)	180(34.1)	43(8.1)
Contact with a friends and acquaintances are	38(7.2)	46(8.7)		54(10.2)	309(58.5)	81(15.3)
Sexual life		32(6.1)	1(.2)	90(17.0)	249(47.2)	156(29.5)
Ability to manage my self-care (dressing, hygiene, transfers, etcetera)	3(.6)	4(.8)	2(.4)	78(14.8)	243(46.0)	198(37.5)
Family life	33(6.3)	4(.8)	1(.2)	9(1.7)	352(66.7)	129(24.4)
Partner relationship	3(.6)	2(.4)	4(.8)	45(8.5)	102(19.3)	372(70.5)

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Table 4 shows that a larger percentage of the respondent (59.7%) reported that their vocational situation is satisfying, a larger percentage of the respondent (72.9%) reported that life as a whole is satisfying, a significant percentage of the respondent (39.9%) reported that their financial situation is satisfying, a significant percentage of the respondent (42.2%) reported that their leisure situation is satisfying, larger percentage of the respondent (73.8%) reported that their contact with their friends and acquaintances are satisfying, a larger percentage of the respondent (76.7%) reported that their sexual life is satisfying, of the respondent (83.5%) reported that their ability to manage to their self-care is satisfying, a larger percentage of the respondent (91.1%) reported that their family life is satisfying, a larger percentage of the respondent (89.8%) reported that their partner relationship is satisfying.

Correlation analyses of all the study variable was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), the resulting output generated and arranged in Table 2:

Table 5: Mean, Standard Deviation and zero Order Correlation matrix showing the Relationship among Variables in the study.

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
LSAT	43.38	6.37	1								
JSAT	85.73	13.73	.43**	1							
PCTR	51.61	6.01	.23**	.55**	1						
PCCD	36.97	7.60	-.15	-.07	.00	1					
PCC	22.15	5.81	-.14	-	0.85	.34**	1				
				.26**							
PCS	17.34	4.48	-.17*	-	-.13	.62**	.62**	1			
				.29**							
PCD	18.31	5.53	-.05	-.19*	-	.61**	.25**	.78**	1		
					.35**						
SE	26.93	3.57	-	-	-	.40**	.12	.34**	.46**	1	
			.36**	.53**	.28**						
GSE	43.21	6.68	.46**	.75**	.56**	-	-.03	-	-	.-	1
						.39**		.29**	.45**	.67**	

**Correlation is significant ($p < 0.01$), *Correlation is significant ($p < 0.05$)

LSAT: Life satisfaction; JSAT: Job satisfaction; PCTR: Personal Career Transition readiness; PCCD: Personal Career Confidence Development; PCC: Personal Career Control; PCS: Personal Career Support; PCD: Personal Career Decision; SE: Self Esteem; GSE: General Self Efficacy

Source: Field Survey, 2016

The results in Table 5 demonstrated that Job satisfaction ($r = .43, p < 0.01$), Personal Career Transition Readiness ($r = .23, p < 0.01$), General Self Efficacy ($r = .46, p < 0.01$) and Satisfaction with life. This demonstrates that life satisfaction increases as job satisfaction was increasing. Employees who are happier with the facets of their job demonstrated high satisfaction than those with low job satisfaction. The result also shows that employees' transition readiness increases satisfaction among those nearing retirement. Employees showing readiness to transit into retirement were more satisfied with life than those who were not ready. Employees showing higher confidence levels as regards their transition and present career situation reported higher satisfaction with life compared to those with lower confidence levels. This shows that Job satisfaction, Career Transition Readiness and General Self Efficacy were positive determinants of satisfaction with life among employees nearing retirement.

In addition, Self Esteem ($r = -.358, p < 0.01$), Personal Career support ($r = -.17, p < 0.01$) were significant inverse correlates of Satisfaction with life. The result demonstrates that satisfaction with life decreases with increasing self-esteem. Employees with high self-esteem displayed low life satisfaction among the employees compared to those with low self-esteem. It was also demonstrated that lower career support was associated with increasing satisfaction with life. This suggests that self-esteem and career support are negative predictors of satisfaction with life. However, Personal Career Confidence Development, Personal Career Control Personal Career Decision were not significant correlates of Satisfaction with life. Meaning that Personal

Career Confidence Development, Personal Career Control Personal Career Decision do not have significant contribution employees pre-retirement satisfaction with life.

Table 6: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of Career Transition readiness, Confidence Development, Career Control, and Career Support, and Career Decision, self-efficacy, self-esteem and job satisfaction on Life satisfaction

Predictors	β	t	P	R	R ²	F	P
Career Transition readiness	.40	5.04	<.05				
Career Confidence Development	.03	.72	>.05				
Career Control	-.31	-6.06	<.001				
Career Support	.49	12.54	<.001	.57	.33	33.22	<.01
Career Decision	.34	4.58	<.001				
Self -efficacy	.43	10.78	<.001				
Self esteem	-.26	-3.12	<.05				
Job satisfaction	.52	9.44	<.001				

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Table 6; the result revealed that career transition readiness, confidence development, career control, career support, career decision influence jointly predicted life satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.33$, $F(8,478) = 33.22$, $p < .01$). The composite influence of career transition readiness, confidence development, career control, career support and decision accounted for 33% of the change observed in the self-report of life satisfaction. The result revealed that career transition readiness ($\beta = .40$, $t = 5.04$, $p < .05$), career control ($\beta = -.31$, $t = -6.06$; $p < .001$), career support ($\beta = -.49$, $t = -12.54$; $p < .001$) personal career decision ($\beta = -.34$, $t = -9.58$; $p < .001$), self-esteem ($\beta = -.26$, $t = -4.92$; $p < .001$), and job satisfaction ($\beta = .52$, $t = 9.44$; $p < .001$), have significant independent influence on life satisfaction. Career Confidence Development ($\beta = .03$, $t = .72$; $p > .05$) have no significant independent influence on life satisfaction. Employees who exhibit proficient career readiness believing that they have good control over their career and career decisions but received low career support were more satisfied with their lives than employees with low control, slow readiness and poor career decisions but high career support.

Discussion

The study investigated satisfaction with life among employees close to retirement in Lagos state public service. The study found that increasing job satisfaction was associated with increasing satisfaction with life. This is supported by Amaike (2006) who demonstrated that good career outcome and income affect perceived level of satisfaction in life. The finding is also similar to Bowling *et al.* (2010) who demonstrated that job satisfaction was related to both positive affect and the absence of negative affect an aspect of satisfaction with life. In the same vein, the finding support Michalos and Orlando, (2006); that positive association exist between happiness and job satisfaction. This is in contrast to Rode (2004) who found that the relationship between job satisfaction and life satisfaction was not significant. These findings support the position of Weiss (2002) who argued that the present nature of the job facet will determine extent to which it

influences present life satisfaction level when compared with past experiences i.e. better pension scheme, available consultancy job etc may have influenced. The reasoning is that personal experience over time may have influence the life satisfaction (Cummins, 2006).

Career transition readiness and career support were correlates of satisfaction with life. This is similar to findings of Vigoda-Gadot, Baruch, and Grimland, (2010) who found that preparations for retirement, social capital, perception of organizational politics in the new working place and work-family conflict are related to retiree's success in their second career. The findings also support the study of Robertson, and Brott, (2014). Who demonstrated that career Control and readiness predicted satisfaction with life. In addition, the finding of this study also support Burke, Burgess, and Fallon, (2006), Bogler and Nir (2011), Joo and Ready (2012) and Karatepe (2012) results regarding the relationship between perceived organizational support and satisfaction.

General self-efficacy and self-esteem were also found to correlates with satisfaction with life. In line with that self-efficacy directly effects career satisfaction (Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2010), Moe, Pazzaglia, and Ronceni, (2010) and Adebomi, Ibitoye, and Sanni, (2012). Post retirement teachers' career satisfaction was positive explained by self-efficacy; hence, employees high on self-efficacy reported higher levels of satisfaction. This finding support the various study which demonstrated that confidence and self-esteem (Heppner, Fuller, and Malton, 1998; Robbins, 1987), control (Strazdins et al., 2004), affects life after retirement among employees. The result is in line in the study conducted by Forough and Azimeh (2012) who found relationship between self-esteem and life satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

This study reveals that job satisfaction, personal career transition readiness, general self-efficacy, self-esteem and personal career support were psychosocial predictors' satisfaction with life among pre-retirement employees in the Lagos state public service. These demonstrate that transition preparedness and good condition of service is what promotes satisfaction with life of employee. One major implication for management is that about to retire may be a great source for new managerial talent, possessing high skills and qualities, and may be instrumental in applying organizational changes if their present working are well motivated and organised. Effective organizational support mechanisms need to be in place, including the career practice of preparation for leaving the organization. Promoting the employability of the about to retire employees would yield long-term bonds with employees at all levels. By doing it right, the organization ensures that employees who leave will play a positive role as 'ambassadors', helping with social/business networking for the organization and for future generations of organizational members.

References

- Adebomi, O., Ibitoye, H. O., and Sanni, O. B. (2012) Job satisfaction and self-efficacy as correlates of job commitment of special education teachers in Oyo State. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(9), 95-103.
- Amake, B. (2006). *Pension Reform Act 2004: socio-economic implications for the public services in Nigeria*. Lagos: Concept.

- Amaike, B., and Lai, O. (2014). Gender differentials in retirement antecedents and life satisfaction of formal sector retirees in Lagos State, Nigeria. *The Journal of Aging in Emerging Economies*. 68-99.
- Asuquo, G.E. (2007). Organizational Leadership and Quality of Care of Nigeria's HIV/AIDS Response, Unpublished Doctorate Dissertation Submitted to St. Clements University.
- Bishop, A. J., Martin, P., and Poon, L. (2006). Happiness and congruence in older adulthood: A structural model of life satisfaction. *Aging and Mental Health*, 10, 445–453.
- Bishop, A. J., Martin, P., and Poon, L. W. (2006). Happiness and congruence in older adulthood: A structural model of life satisfaction. *Aging and Mental Health*, 10, 1-9.
- Bogler, R., and Nir, A. E. (2011). The importance of teachers' perceived organizational support to job satisfaction: What's empowerment got to do with it? *Journal of Educational Administration*, 50(3), 287-306.
- Bowling, N. A. (2010), "Effects of Job Satisfaction and Conscientiousness on Extra-Role Behaviours", *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 25(1), 119-130
- Bowling, N., Eschelman, K. J., and Wang, Q. (2010). A Meta-analytic examination of the relationship between job satisfaction and subjective well-being. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*. 83. 915-934.
- Burke, R. J., Burgess, Z., and Fallon, B. (2006). Organizational practices supporting women and their satisfaction and well being. *Women in Management Review*, 21(5), 416-425.
- Cummins, R. (2006). Personal wellbeing index-adult (4th ed.). School of Psychology, Deakin University.
- Diner, E. (2008). "Myths in the Science of Happiness, and Directions for Future Research," *The Science of Subjective Well-Being*, M. Eid and R. J. Larsen (eds.), New York: Guilford Press: 493-514.
- Diner, E., and Fujita, F. (1997). Social comparisons and subjective wellbeing. In B. B. R. Gibbons (Ed.), *Health, coping, and social comparison* (pp. 329—357).
- Forough Bozorgpour and Azimeh Salimi (2012). State Self-Esteem, Loneliness and Life Satisfaction. Department of Clinical psychology, University of Shiraz, Shiraz, Iran. Department of Educational psychology, University of Shiraz, Shiraz, Iran. International Conference on Education and Educational Psychology.
- Friedmann, E.A. and R.J. Havighurst. (1954). *The Meaning of Work and Retirement*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- George, L. and Bearnon, L. (1980). *Quality of life in older persons*. New York; Human Science Press.

- Heppner, M. J., Fuller, B. E., and Malton, K. D. (1998). Adults in involuntary career transition: an analysis of the relationship between the psychological and career domains. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 6, 329-346.
- Joo, B. K. B. and Ready, K. J. (2012). Career satisfaction: The influences of proactive personality, performance goal orientation, organizational learning culture, and leader-member exchange quality. *Career Development International*, 17(3), 276-295.
- Judge, T.A., Erez, A., and Bono, J.E. (1998). The power of being positive: The relation between positive self-concept and job performance. *Human Performance*, 11, 167-187.
- Kapteyn, A., Smith, J. and Van Soest, A. (2009). "Life Satisfaction". Discussion Paper, No. 4015, Institute for the Study of Labour.
- Karatepe, O. M. (2012). Perceived organizational support, career satisfaction, and performance outcomes: A study of hotel employees in Cameroon. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 24(5), 735-752.
- Kosloski, K., G. Ginsburg, and C.W. Backman. 1994. "Retirement as a Process of Active Role Transition." In V.L. Allen and E. van de Vliert (Eds.), *Role Transitions: Explorations and Explanations*. New York: Plenum Press.
- Lachlan Heybroek (2011). Life Satisfaction and Retirement: A Latent Growth Mixture Modelling Approach. School of Social Science, University of Queensland. Survey 10th Anniversary Research Conference 2011, University of Melbourne.
- Lachlan Heybroek, Michele Haynes and Janeen Baxter (2015). Life Satisfaction and Retirement in Australia: A Longitudinal Approach. *Work, Aging and Retirement*. 1, (2) 166–180 doi:10.1093/workar/wav006 Advance Access publication.
- Locke, E. A. (1976), *The Nature and Causes Of Job Satisfaction*. *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology*, Chicago: Rand McNally, 1319-1328.
- McKnight CG, Huebner ES, and Suldo S. (2002): Relationships among stressful life events, temperament, problem behavior, and global life satisfaction in adolescents. *Psychology in the Schools*. (2002);39(6):677–687. doi: 10.1002/pits.10062.
- McKnight CG, Huebner ES, Seldom S. (2002) Relationships among stressful life events, temperament, problem behaviour, and global life satisfaction in adolescents. *Psychology in the Schools*. 2002; 39(6):677–687.
- Michalos, A. C, and Orlando, J. A. (2006). Quality of life of some under-represented survey respondents: Youth, aboriginals and unemployed. *Social Indicators Research*, 79, 191-213.
- Miller, S.J. (1965). "The Social Dilemma of the Aging Leisure Participant." In A.M. Rose and W. A. Peterson (Eds.), *Older People and Their Social World*. Philadelphia: F.A. Davis

- Moe, A., Pazzaglia, F., and Ronceni, L. (2010). When being able is not enough. The combined value of positive affect and self-efficacy for job satisfaction in teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26, 1145-1153.
- Pivot, W. (2008). "The Assessment of Subjective Well-Being: Successes and Shortfalls, the Science of Subjective Well-Being," IN M. Eid and R. J. Larsen (eds.), New York: Guilford Press: 124-140.
- Pavot, W. and Diener, E. (2008). The Satisfaction with Life Scale and the emerging construct of life satisfaction. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 3, 137-152.
- Robertson, H. C. (2010). Life Satisfaction among Midlife Career Changers: A Study of Military Members Transitioning to Teaching. Published PhD dissertation, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Virginia.
- Robertson, H.C. and Brott, P.E. (2014). Military Veterans' midlife career transition and life satisfaction. *The Professional Counsellor*, 4, 139-149.
- Rode, J.C (2004) Job satisfaction and life satisfaction revisited: A longitudinal test of an integrated model *Human Relations* .57: 1205-1230, doi:10.1177/0018726704047143
- Rosenberg, M. (1965). *Society and the adolescent self-image*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Russell, R. V. (1984). *Correlates of life satisfaction in retirement*. AM Arbor, MI:
- Spector, P. E. (1985), "Measurement of Human Service Staff Satisfaction: Development of the Job Satisfaction Survey", *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 13(6), 693-713.
- Trazdins, L., D'Souza, R.M., Lim, L., Broom, D.H. and Rodgers, B. (2004). Job strain, job insecurity, and health: rethinking the relationship. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 9, 4, 296-305.
- Seldom SM, Huebner ES. (2006) Is extremely high life satisfaction during adolescence advantageous? *Social Indicators Research*. ; 78(2):179–203.
- Szinovacz, M.E. (2003) 'Contexts and pathways: Retirement as institution, process, and experience', pp. 6-52 in G.A. Adams and T.A. Beehr (eds) *Retirement: Reasons, Processes, and Results*. New York: Springer Publishing Company. University Microfilms International.
- Vigoda-Gadot E, Baruch Y, Grimland, S. (2010). Career transitions: an empirical examination of second career of military retirees. *Public Personnel Management*; 39(4): 379–404.

- Wang, M. (2007) 'Profiling Retirees in the Retirement Transition and Adjustment Process: Examining the Longitudinal Change Patterns of Retirees' Psychological Well-Being', *Journal of Applied Psychology* 92(2): 455-74
- Weiss, D.J., Dawis, R.V., England, G.W., and Lofquist, L.H. (1967). *Manual for the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota.
- Weiss, H.M. (2002). Deconstructing job satisfaction: Separating evaluations, beliefs and affective experiences. *Human Resource Management Review*, 12, 173-194.
- Zabelina, D. L and Robinson, M. D. (2010). Don't be so hard on yourself: Self-compassion facilitates creative originality among self-judgmental individuals. *Creativity Research Journal*, 22, 288-293.